

THE IMPACT OF ALISHER NAVOI AND ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD BOBUR'S MASTERPIECES ON RENAISSANCE IN XV CENTURY AS WELL AS THEIR ROLE IN SOCIETY.

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ABSTRACT: In this article the works of Alisher Navoi and Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur will be studied in detail. As it can be observed, both of this genius poets have written a number of books which had a huge influence on community for improving the way of their lifestyles and also it will be explained the reason why dwellers of past time have respect for these kind of scientists.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье будет подробно изучено творчество Алишера Навои и Захириддина Мухаммада Бобура. Как можно заметить, оба этих гениальных поэта написали ряд книг, которые оказали огромное влияние на общество для улучшения их образа жизни, а также будет объяснена причина, по которой жители прошлого времени уважали такого рода

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada Alisher Navoiy va Boburning jamiyatga keltirgan foydasi va shuningdek 15-asrdagi uyg'onish davriga qo'shgan hissasi haqida gapiriladi. Shuningdek, ular jamiyat hayotidagi muammolarni qanday hal etishgani va hurmat qozonishning sababi aytiladi.

Kalit so'zlar : Uyg'onish davri ,insoniy muhabbat ,adabiy hayot, kuchli imperiya ziyoli odamlar Javohir La'l Neru.

Ключевые слова: Ренессанс, человеческая любовь, литературная жизнь, сильная империя, образованные люди Джавохир Лал Неру.

Evident is the fact that one of the greatest poets of the world was Alisher Navoi in the XV century . Not only this person wrote books about the social life of dwellers, but also tried to

deal with mankind problems with the help of demonstrating their issues on his books. As it has been mentioned above Alisher Navoi as well as Bobur played a vital role in second renaissance. This article will analyse how they managed to this and provides striking data about their knowledge as well. During the reign of Amir Timur many people who have the intention to research in science were gathered in one place such as greatest historian Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy , Hofiz She'roziy and also the descendants of this person were also the leaders of that time. They built a great number of monuments, mosques ranging from Shohi Zinda to mausoleum of Ahmad Yassavi and created opportunites for scientists in attempt to carry out more researchs. This kind of work was continued by the heirs of Timur and Alisher Navoi also studied in the capital of Amir Timur's country :Samarkhand .In his autobiographic books he mentioned Samarkhand as paradise. From his childhood Navoi was immersed in literature of Turkish language and during his meaningful life tried to prevent this language from being dead language like Latin. One of the main reasons why Alisher Navoi succeeded in his sphere is that young poet was brought up in the atmosphere of literary culture. There was an interesting fact about Navoi which shows that at the of seven he astonished ninety nine years old poet Lutfiy with his ability to write poems. As a child , he memorized Fariddin Attar's ' Mantiq ut-tayr' and came to the attention of Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy.

Orazin yopg'och ko'zimdin sochilur har lahza yosh,
Bo'ylakim paydo bo'lur yulduz nihon bo'lg'och quyosh.

As he grew older, he realised the main meaning of life , the mistakes of human beings and in his books called ' Mahbub ul-qulub' , 'Hayrat ul-abror' he tried to show and analyse them. For instance, candle is always straight as it lights up and makes everybody blissfully happy or if ruler is straight your draw will be correct as well as beautiful.(1) These sentences, if it is thought logically , were written in order to show people the right way. His life was united with Hussein Boykaro who gave the title of 'muqarrabi hazrati sultani' (the closest person to the sultan' to Navoi. Nizomiddin Mir Alisher Navoi

gave a contribution to the sultan and made ready many knowledgeable person like Kamoliddin Bekhzod (Famous painter) , Xondamir (historian), Binoiy (poet) .Without any doubt it can be concluded , where are more enlightened people, there will be progress in terms of social and academic life. So Navoi had a huge influence on second renaissance.

Why did they dawn while turning flavescent its frontispiece?
Because of hidden sun was it sick more than I miss?
If it were not mad like me, showing craziness in full ,
Like Mejnun –over the hills ---would not tear its chemise.
Does the dawn have covert spots from the parting of the sun?
Otherwise –these star –like drops –would it on its face release?
Do not say the reddish clouds ‘re sailing now in the sky,
In fact they are the bloody cotton affected by belly’s caprice.
They are not sunrays you see, but because of my mourning –
It’s daybreak –with nail of stars –on its face could cause disease.
Hey cupbearer , give us now now a morning wine to take delight ,
So that when we leave this world the peep morning will increase
Be like humble, bowing flower , be like a nightingale awake,
Hey Navoi , in this garden if you want to live in peace.(2)

As regards with Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur he was one of the knowledgeable descendants of Timur and was the founder of the Mugal Empire and the Emprorer of the Mughal dynasty. It should be noted that in addition to being emperor he was also famous poet and write. One of the important aspects of his work is the glorification of a truly human , patriot, genuine love. As a novelist he wrote ‚Baburnoma’ which is considered to be useful book for some wanted to learn about the history , geography of 15- th century. In spite of the fact that he could not persue his dreams in Movorounnahr , he established his empire in India and this lasted 332 years. Babur’s role in indian society is that he banned burning widow and also tried to build more buildings. Now we can see Indians are immensely

grateful that during his dynasty their country developed. Javohar La'l Neru once said that : Babur is a unique person with his abilities'(3) All in all both of them have a huge impact on our society although they have already died , their works are still alive in our heart.

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